

MATEMATIK SAVODXONLIKNING DARAJALARI

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Farg‘ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani
2 son kasb hunar maktabi
matematika fani o‘qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada matematika fanining savodxonlik darajalari tahlil etilib, misollar bilan tahlil etiladi. Matematik savodxonlikning birinchi darajasi: qayta tiklash (takrorlash), ta'riflash va hisoblashlarga misollar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: hunar, daraja, misol, javob, test

Аннотация: В статье анализируются уровни математической грамотности и анализируются на примерах. Первый уровень математической грамотности: приведены примеры восстановления (повторения), описания и расчета.

Ключевые слова: навык, уровень, пример, ответ, тест.

Abstract: The article analyzes the levels of mathematical literacy and analyzes them with examples. First level of mathematical literacy: examples of reconstruction (repetition), description and calculation are given.

Key words: skill, level, example, answer, test.

Kasb hunar maktablari o'quvchilarini matematika faniga qiziqishlarini oshirish, matematik savodxonligini oshirish dolzarb masaladir. Matematik savodxonlikning birinchi darajasi: qayta tiklash (takrorlash), ta'riflash va hisoblashlar.

Birinchi darajadagi kompetensiyalar ko'plab standartlashtirilgan testlarda, shuningdek, qiyosiy xalqaro tadqiqotlar bilan, asosan, javoblarni tanlab olish topshiriqlari kabi vazifalar shaklida sinovdan o'tgan faoliyatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu kompetentlik darajasi turli faktlarni bilish, xossalarni qayta tiklash, tengdosh matematik obyektlarni taniy olish, standart algoritm va tartiblarni amalga oshirish, standart usullari va algoritmik ko'nikmalardan foydalanish.

Misol 1. Miqdorlari teng bo'lgan ikki g'ildirakli va uch g'ildirakli velosipedlar bolalar o'yinchoq do'konida sotilmoqda. Barcha velosipedlar g'ildiraklari umumiy soni qancha bo'lishi mumkin?

A) 16; B) 24; C) 25; D) 28; Ye) 33.

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Yechish. Ikki va uch g'ildirakli velosipedlar soni teng bo'lgani uchun ularning g'ildiraklari soni 5 ga karrali bo'lishi kerak.

To'g'ri javob: S.

Misol 2. Xaridor mavsum paytida narxi 750 ming so'm bo'lgan qishki 44 Matematika fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovasiyalar moduli bo'yicha o'quv-uslubiy majmua ko'ylakni arzon narxlarda sotish paytida chegirma narxida 300 ming so'mga sotib oldi. Xaridor necha foiz mablag'ini iqtisod qilgan? A) 60%; B) 150%; C) 90%; D) 87,5%; E) 78,5% Yechish. CHegirma narxi mavsumiy narxdan ($750000 - 300000 = 450000$) 450 ming so'm kam bo'lganligi sababli, bu farq mavsumiy bahoning necha foizini topish lozim bo'ladi, ya'ni 450000 soni 750000 ning necha foizini tashkil qilishini topamiz. To'g'ri javob: A.

Misol 3. Uchta do'st sayohatga o'tlanishdi va chodir sotib olishga qaror qilishdi Ularning birinchi chodir narxining 60% ni, ikkinchisi narxning qolgan qismining 40 % ni, uchinchi esa - oxirgi 30 dollarni to'ladi. CHodir qancha turadi?

A) 120 dollar; B) 150 dollar; C) 90 dollar; D) 125 dollar; E) 100 dollar.

Yechish. Faraz qilaylik, chodir narxi x dollar bo'lsin. Unda ularning birinchi: $0,6x$ ikkinchisi: $- 0,4x \cdot 0,6 = 0,16x$, uchinchi $x - (0,6x + 0,16x) = 0,24x$ dollar to'lagan. SHartga ko'ra, uchinchi do'st 30 dollar to'lagan. Demak, $0,24x = 30$ yoki $x = 125$. CHodirning narxi 125 dollar. To'g'ri javob. D.

2. Matematik savodxonlikning ikkinchi darajasi: muammoni hal qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan aloqalar va bog'lanishni aniqlash. Ikkinchi darajali kompetensiyalar qo'yilgan oddiy muammolarini hal qilish uchun matematikaning turli sohalari, bo'limlari va mavzulari orasida bog'lanishlarni aniqlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu vazifalarni standart vazifalarga kiritib bo'lmaydi, lekin ularda ko'rilyotgan vaziyat chuqurroq matematik bilimlarni talab qiladi. Ushbu kompetensiya darajasida o'quvchilar topshiriq shartiga ko'ra berilgan ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish va bu vazifaga muvofiq muammoni qo'yish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lishlari kerak bo'ladi. Matematika turli bo'limlari materiallari orasidagi aloqalarni o'rnatishda o'quvchilardan tushunchalarni, shartlarni, isbotlarni, tasdiqlarni, misollarni farqlash va ularni o'zaro bog'lash qobiliyatiga ega bo'lishlari talab etiladi. Ushbu kompetensiya

darajasi shuningdek turli belgilar bilan rasmiylashtirilgan tilda yozilgan yozuvlarning mazmunini tushuntirish va sharhlash, ularni umumiy tilga tarjima qilish qobiliyatini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu kompetensiya darajasiga bog'liq bo'lgan vazifalar nuqtai nazaridan, o'quvchilar vaziyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga bog'liq qaror qabul qilishni talab qiladigan muayyan holatni taklif qilishadi.

45 Matematika fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovasiyalar moduli bo'yicha o'quv-uslubiy majmua Misol 1. Tadbirkorlik ko'lamini rivojlantirish uchun ikki sherik 50 ming dollar ajratdi. Bozorda narxlarning o'zgarishi munosabati bilan birinchisi o'z ulushini 30 foizga, ikkinchisi esa 70 foizga oshirdi. Natijada ularning umumiy kapitali 81 ming dollarga teng bo'ldi. Har bir sherik qancha hissa qo'shgan? Yechish. Bu holatni ikki o'zgaruvchili chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi sifatida modellashtirish mumkin. Aytaylik, x - birinchi sherikning hissasi, y - ikkinchicining hissasi bo'lsin. Narxlar o'sishidan keyin birinchi sherik hissasi - $1,3x$, ikkinchi sherik hissasi esa $1,7y$ ga teng bo'ladi. Chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasiga ega bo'lamiz: $x + y = 50000$, $1,3x + 1,7y = 81000$. Uni yechib, birinchi tadbirkor 13 ming, ikkinchisi esa 68 ming dollar hissa qo'shganini topamiz.

Misol 2. Uch do'st o'yin o'ynadi. O'yinni olib boruvchi 1 dan 8 gacha raqamlar bilan raqamlangan kartalarni ikkita o'yinchiga tarqatadi. Birinchi o'yinchiga 3 ta, ikkinchisiga esa 5 ta karta tarqatdi. Natijada ulardagi kartalar raqamlari yig'indisi har ikkalasida ham bir xil bo'ldi. Uchinchi ishtirokchi quyidagi fikrlarni aytdi: 1) ikkinchi o'yinchida uchta karta toq raqamli; 2) 2 raqamli karta ikkinchi o'yinchida; 3) 1 raqamli karta birinchi o'yinchida emas. U haqmi? Yechish. O'yinchilardagi kartalar raqamlari yig'indisi bir xil bo'lgani, ular 1 dan 8 gacha barcha sonlar yig'indisining yarmini tashkil etadi. Demak, ulardagi kartalar raqamlari yig'indisi $(1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8=36)$ yarmi) 18 ga teng. Demak, uchta kartasi bor birinchi o'yinchida raqamlari 5, 6 va 7 yoki 3, 7, 8 raqamli kartalari bo'lishi mumkin. Chunki, boshqa hollarda kartalar raqamlar yig'indisi 18 dan kichik bo'ladi. Unda ikkinchi o'yinchida raqamlari 1, 2, 3, 4 va 8 yoki 1, 2, 3, 5 va

7 yoki 1, 2, 4, 5 va 6 ga teng kartochkalar bo'lishi mumkin. SHunday qilib, birinchi fikr noto'g'ri, ikkinchisi va uchinchisi to'g'ri. Javob: 1) Yo'q, 2) Ha, 3) Ha. Misol 3. Matematik yo'l halokatiga guvoh bo'lib, quyidagilarni eslab qoldi: Aybdor avtomobilining raqami to'rt xonali son bo'lib, u 19 ga bo'linadi va 19 soni bilan tugaydi. Aybdorni topish uchun avtomobil inspeksiyasi xodimlari nechta avtomobilni tekshirib chiqishlari lozim? Yechish.. Aytaylik, avtomobil raqami A sonidan iborat bo'lsin. Unda $A - 19$ soni ham 19 ga karrali bo'ladi. Ikkinchi tomondan $A - 19 = k \times 19 = b \times 100$. 19 va 100 sonlari o'zaro tub sonlar. Demak, yuzlar soni ham 19 ga bo'linadi. Bunday sonlar bor yo'g'i 5 ta: 19, 38, 57, 76 va 95. Demak, faqat raqami 1919, 3819, 5719, 7619 va 9519 bo'lgan beshta avtomobilni tekshirish lozim.

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